

Towards Fabrication of High-precision Microlens Arrays for LED-based Optoelectronic Devices

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Motivation

- Optical system miniaturization trend has revealed a strong need in microoptics (e.g., microlens array (MLA))
- Microscale optics cannot be produced with conventional lens manufacturing methods, but require more sophisticated approach
- Microoptics is used for collimating or focusing (e.g., laser arrays, detector arrays, fibre optics, sensors, optical interconnects, and optical computing), illumination (e.g., flat panel displays, TV projection systems, retro-reflectors, and diffusers) and imaging (e.g., photocopiers, 3D-photography, signal and image processing, fiber optic couplers, maskless lithography, shop testing, and astronomy)

Fabrication Steps

Geometrical Description

Fabrication parameters are determined by required lens properties

$$f = \frac{R}{n-1}, \quad R = \frac{h^2 + r^2}{2h}$$

$$\frac{r}{10} \leq h \leq \frac{r}{5}, \quad h = \gamma t, \quad \gamma = 1.3 - 1.7$$

f – focal length, R – surface radius of curvature, r – lens/blank radius*, h – max lens thickness, t – blank height*, γ – thermal reflow expansion coefficient

* Parameters that are predetermined at the fabrication process

Fabrication Precision

- Precise controlled spin-coating is the key step for the device fabrication process
- This step defines height, radius of curvature, and focal length of microlenses
- Resist thickness has to be well-defined and uniform over the whole array area
- Resist thickness deviation of $\pm 2 \mu\text{m}$ leads to $125 \mu\text{m}$ change in focal length, which can bring to inhomogeneous pattern at the detection plane

Optical Characterization

- MLA is illuminated through the aperture
- Microscope objective focus is gradually moved in z-direction from the substrate up to MLA focal plane
- Evolution of the light beam is observed and captured with the camera

Focal Length Measurement

50 μm microlens array

100 μm microlens array

Shape and Surface Control

- Main condition for obtaining semi-spherical shape:

$$\frac{r}{10} \leq h \leq \frac{r}{5}$$

- 3D confocal laser scanning microscopy gives a good overview on a lens shape

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